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Chinese Investment Impact on the South Asian Sustainable Infrastructure Development: A Case of Bangladesh Study

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ABSTRACT

The importance of sustainable infrastructure investment plays a key role in promoting and maintaining economic growth. Designed suitable and sustainable infrastructure can also make growth more inclusive by sharing its benefits with poorer units, communities, especially by connecting remote areas, small and landlocked countries with major business centers. Although the South Asia region has made progress in infrastructure development, its growth still can't meet the sustainable international standard for quantity and quality. Insufficient sustainable infrastructure could hinder the potential economic growth of South Asian countries, weaken their international competitiveness and disadvantageously affect their poverty reduction efforts.

Based on the recent estimation of financial demand for sustainable infrastructure in South Asian countries, this paper analyzes the sustainable infrastructure and estimates the external effects of its investments, then research the investment development in South Asia as well Bangladesh. It also quantitatively assessed the welfare impact of regional sustainable infrastructure development on the overall economy of South Asian countries. The situation and impact of the recent economic and financial crisis provide several reasons for the further development of sustainable infrastructure in South Asian regions, especially Bangladesh.

This paper also estimates the need for sustainable infrastructure investment, including transport, electricity, etc. during 2010-2020, to meet growing demands for services and facilitate further rapid growth in the south Asian regions.

Keywords

Bangladesh, South Asia, Connectivity, Sustainability, Infrastructure, FDI, GDP, Investment and Financing, Trade.

1. Introduction

Bangladesh's geographical location between two major regions of Asia—South Asia and Southeast Asia—provides a unique opportunity for the country to benefit from the greater cross-border movement of international business, investment, and enhanced human contact. Bangladesh's economy has grown at a strong clip in recent years, and it has become a development engine in South Asia. In recent years under foreign investment, the overall level of Bangladesh's economic development has shown a steady growth momentum, and the main economic indicators such as GDP, foreign exchange reserves, overseas remittance, exports, and foreign investment. Although, Bangladesh's economic development is restricted by some major problems: fierce confrontational politics, heavy dependence on foreign aid, less electricity, short energy supplies, and product structure. In the next few years, the relatively sustainable infrastructure stably guarantees the main sources of Bangladesh's economic income: export of textile industry, overseas remittance, agriculture, leather, and new dream become from IT.

However, the Bangladesh government has realized the "Golden Bangladesh Dream" and launched a series of economic and social development plans, including infrastructure, IT, energy and power, transportation, communication, chemical industry, textile, and garment industries, and made great efforts to implement the industrialization strategy. Actively encourage and attract domestic private enterprises and foreign investment by establishing economic zones, high-tech parks, and export processing zones. The government of Bangladesh plans to build 100 new economic zones by 2030, and the construction of relevant economic zones is being actively promoted. It is a good announcement from the Bangladesh government in South Asia. In addition, to fulfill the "Golden Bangladesh Dream", the Bangladesh government also needs to care more and more about low-income people especially peasants for their standard life in Bangladesh otherwise it will be very difficult to achieve the "Golden Bangladesh Dream". This is the perfect time for Bangladesh to realize some different packages for low and low-middle-income class, peasants, senior citizens, children, and especially the need to create more and more new job opportunities for the unemployed group. For the problems above, Bangladesh can study from China how to solve those problems 30 years ago.

This paper analyzes infrastructure main features, South Asian sustainable infrastructure needs, National infrastructure financing needs, Chinese investment in South Asia, Challenges for regional sustainable infrastructure, Chinese trade and investment with Bangladesh, connectivity initiatives between Bangladesh, East and South Asian countries, and proposes suggestions for strengthening those initiatives to reap the benefits.

2. Sustainable Infrastructure Main Features

Sustainable infrastructure systems include airports, railways, roads, electricity, gas, water, transport, utilities, and communication technology services. They provide services for businesses, investments, and households. Sustainable infrastructure systems have the following characteristics that demand public sector involvement.

(i) They have public goods, which inhibit private firms; (ii) create positive and negative externalities that

will not take fully into account; (iii) entail a long project cycle and huge costs that private enterprises in developing countries;(iv) require land use that cannot be accomplished without assistance from the government; and (v) need appropriate public sector policies and regulation, as sometimes the provision of utilities can only be done through local monopolies.

2.1. A Scenario for Infrastructure Development in South Asia

According to the economic development in South Asia, the Asian Development Bank Institute (2009) estimated the demand for financing sustainable infrastructure investment during 2010–2020 in 8 South Asian developing countries. If this demand is met, the aggregate sustainable infrastructure stock of these countries would increase by 93.3% in 2020 (Table 1). The power sector would record the fastest growth, with an expansion of 147.6% in the value of sustainable infrastructure stock during the period.

Transport and telecommunication sustainable infrastructure in South Asian countries would increase with humility, by 67.1% and 37.1%, respectively. Geographically, the growth of sustainable infrastructure stock would be rapid in Bangladesh, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, India, and other south Asian countries, but relatively slow in Bhutan and Nepal. Southeast Asian countries would register a comparatively large expansion in telecommunication, energy, transport, and sustainable infrastructure during 2011–2020.

Table1: Projected Growth of Sustainable Infrastructure in South Asian Developing Countries, 2010–2020

Country/region	Transport	Telecommunication	Power	Others	Total
Bangladesh	33.9	84.5	150.7	28.6	72.0
India	73.4	94.1	188.9	20.9	101.0
Pakistan	36.5	28.1	121.0	22.0	58.3
Sri Lanka	39.2	41.7	71.3	10.5	41.6
Nepal	28.5	70.5	130.2	25.2	70.2
Bhutan	22.7	65.3	110.0	22.2	65.2
Maldives	21.8	62.4	101.0	18.6	58.9

Source: Author’s calculation based on: Asian Development Bank Institute (ADBI). 2009. Demand for Infrastructure Financing in Asia 2010–2020. Tokyo: ADBI.

Table 2: Sustainable Infrastructure Coverage in South Asia

Country Name	1991	2001	2005	Growth Rate (%)*	
				1991–2005	2001–2005
Road density (km per sq km of surface area)					
Bangladesh	0.098	0.144	0.150	4.422	0.963
Bhutan	0.051	0.072	0.171	19.608	34.522

India	0.715	1.018	1.100	4.592	2.233
Nepal	0.047	0.090	0.118	12.589	7.835
Pakistan	0.223	0.324	0.325	3.812	0.102
Sri Lanka	1.476	1.512	1.483	0.040	-0.479
Railway density (km per 1000 sq km of surface area)					
Bangladesh	19.067	19.063	19.826	0.332	1.001
India	19.000	19.092	19.264	0.116	0.226
Pakistan	11.022	9.786	9.786	-0.934	0.000
Sri Lanka	22.283	22.085	22.085	-0.074	0.000
Air transport, passengers carried per 1000 population					
Bangladesh	9.589	11.030	11.525	1.682	1.123
Bhutan	13.324	57.668	77.111	39.895	8.429
India	12.368	16.332	25.149	8.612	13.496
Nepal	32.351	25.671	17.701	-3.774	-7.762
Pakistan	46.932	42.502	34.436	-2.219	-4.744
Sri Lanka	51.700	91.732	143.57	14.809	14.130
Maldives	42.222	188.69	248.92	40.796	7.979
Maritime cargo (million tonnes per seaport)					
Bangladesh	1.900	3.835	4.129	9.737	1.858
India	14.158	29.469	48.905	20.452	16.488
Pakistan	11.290	13.345	26.445	11.186	24.541
Sri Lanka	6.254	8.247	13.143	9.179	14.842
Fixed-line and mobile phone subscribers (per 1000 population)					
Bangladesh	2.081	5.975	71.004	276.001	272.076
Bhutan	4.164	23.418	110.81	213.445	93.304
India	6.705	35.449	127.67	150.347	65.041
Nepal	3.312	11.343	25.706	56.346	31.656
Pakistan	10.155	24.333	115.86	86.748	94.040
Sri Lanka	7.402	61.863	234.68	255.879	69.840
Maldives	34.276	110.50	564.06	128.805	102.609

Electric power consumption (kWh)					
Bangladesh	50.012	103.58	139.55	14.92	8.680
India	295.3	402.1	457.33	4.613	4.852
Nepal	36.85	87.64	68.820	7.231	4.853
Pakistan	297.27	373.55	425.03	3.582	3.445
Sri Lanka	160.13	276.67	344.16	9.577	6.099

Note: * Annual average growth rate km = kilometer, kWh = kilowatt-hour, sq = square. Source: De (2009).

2.2. Sustainable Infrastructure Connectivity and Competitiveness in South Asia

The development of sustainable infrastructure networks and connectivity is essential for the integration of core and wider economic activities and basic services in the country. The latest World Economic Forum (2010) Global Competitiveness Report and the infrastructure quality assessment included therein illustrate the importance of infrastructure quality in global competitiveness (Table 3). In addition, various studies have shown that the quality and breadth of infrastructure networks have greatly affected economic growth and reduced income inequality and poverty (ADB / ADBI, 2009).

Table 3: Ranking and Score of Competitiveness Index and Infrastructure Quality Assessment of Selected Countries in South Asia

Economy	2009/2010			
	GCI		Infrastructure	
	Rank	Score	Rank	Score

Bangladesh	106	3.55	126	2.39
India	49	4.30	76	3.41
Pakistan	101	3.58	89	3.06
Nepal	125	3.34	131	2.03
Sri Lanka	79	4.01	64	3.88

Note: Ranking out of 133 total countries surveyed Source: World Economic Forum (2010) Score: 1–poorly developed, inefficient; 7–among the best in the world

3. National Financing Needs for South Asia Connectivity

From 2010 to 2020, the 8 ADB developing member countries covered in this paper are expected to need almost US\$2.37 trillion (in 2008 US\$) for sustainable infrastructure investment which total need in Asia around US\$8.22 trillion. Around 64% of this is needed for new capacity investments in infrastructure and around 32% is needed for maintenance or replacement of existing assets. Among the South Asian countries, Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan are the three countries with the highest demand for sustainable infrastructure investment. Overall, the top four countries constitute 90% of the total infrastructure investment demand most of which are in South Asia (Table 4).

Table 4: National Infrastructure Investment Needs for South Asian connectivity: 2010-2020

Country/Region	% of Total Asian Investment Need	Estimated Investment Needs (US\$ million)	Investments as Percentage of Total		Total Investment per Year	Total Investment Per Capita (US\$)	Per Capita (Constant 2000 US\$)
			New Capacity	Maintenance			
South Asia	28.829% (need in Asia)	2,370,497	63%	37%	215,500	1,756	685
Bangladesh	1.762%	144,903	54%	46%	13,173	906	462
Bhutan	0.011%	886	30%	70%	81	1,291	1,247
India	26.421%	2,172,469	64%	36%	197,497	1,906	718
Nepal	0.174%	14,330	50%	50%	1,303	497	254

Sri Lanka	0.461%	37,908	52%	48%	3,446	1,881	1,199
Pakistan	1.86%	156303	50%	50%	12,382	904	458

The estimated value in this study is comparable to similar national forecasts in other existing studies focusing on similar time frames. The total sustainable infrastructure investment demand includes Bangladesh, Pakistan, India, and Sri Lanka. Moreover, some country estimates have been revised upwards, taking into account the latest data and economic projections.

Table 5,6 shows the breakdown of investment needs by sector among the south Asian countries and presents national investment needs by sector for the top 4 economies in South Asia. In general, energy and transport are the largest components of infrastructure investment demand in South Asia. By sub-region, South Asia has the largest investment demand of US \$2.37 trillion or 29% for total in Asian countries.

**Table 5: National Sustainable Infrastructure Investment Needs in South Asia, 2010-2020:
Per Sub-region and Per Sector (2008 US\$ billions)**

Country/Region	Transportation	Electricity	Telecommunications	Water and Sanitation
Bangladesh	180	100	70	10
India	195	275	75	16
Pakistan	170	95	65	12
Sri Lanka	170	90	55	12
Nepal	160	48	60	12
Bhutan	165	0.00	60	13
Maldives	152	65	55	11

Source: Author, ADB/ADBI (2009)

Sustainable infrastructure development is essential for sustainable economic growth and productivity in developing countries. According to a joint study by the Asian Development Bank (ADB) and the Asian Development Bank Institute (ADBI) (2009), the difference in infrastructure development accounts for one-third of the overall difference in per capita output of workers in South and East Asia. Due to the huge financing gap, the benefits of infrastructure development have not been fully realized in South Asia. The financing gap between 2016 and 2030 is estimated to be about US \$22.5 trillion (2015 price), or about US \$1.5 trillion per year on average (Asian Development Bank 2017; Table 6)

Table 6: South Asia's Sustainable Infrastructure Needs for 2016–2030

Region	Projecte	2030 UN	2030	Baseline Estimates	Climate Change–
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	d Annual GDP Growth	Populatio n Projection (billion)	Projecte d GDP per Capital (2015 \$)			Adjusted Estimates**	
				Investmen t Needs (billion)	Investmen t Needs as% of GDP	Investmen t Needs (billion)	Investmen t Needs as% of GDP
Central Asia	3.1	0.096	6,202	492	6.8	565	7.8
East Asia	5.1	1.503	18,602	13,781	4.5	16,062	5.2
South Asia*	6.5	2.059	3,446	5,477	7.6	6,347	8.8
Southeas t Asia	5.1	0.723	7,040	2,759	5.0	3,147	5.7
Pacific	3.1	0.014	2,889	42	8.2	46	9.1
Asia and the Pacific	5.3	4.396	9,227	22,551	5.1	26,166	5.9

GDP = gross domestic product, UN = United Nations.* Pakistan and Afghanistan are included in South Asia.

** Includes climate-mitigation and climate-proofing costs, but not other adaptation costs, especially those associated with sea-level rise. Source: ADB (2017).

According to the study, the largest investment demand faced by the transport sector in the South Asian sub-region is estimated at \$1.2 trillion. This was followed by the telecommunications sector, and then the water and sanitation sector.

The relationship between the national infrastructure investment demand and the estimated GDP, further shows how big the demand is. As can be seen in Table 7, South Asia will need to invest approximately 11% of its GDP to meet rising demands for sustainable infrastructure services.

Table 7: Sustainable Infrastructure Investment Needs as a % of Estimated GDP in South Asia 2010-2020

Country	Investment as % of Estimated GDP				
	Transport	Electricity	ITC	Water and Sanitation	Total
Bangladesh	4.92%	1.24%	4.22%	1.19%	11.56%

Bhutan	2.84%	0.00%	0.87%	0.36%	4.07%
India	5.67%	3.23%	1.87%	0.34%	11.12%
Nepal	1.65%	0.58%	5.14%	1.10%	8.48%
Sri Lanka	4.23%	1.00%	1.39%	0.22%	6.85%
Pakistan	4.56%	1.1%	2.1%	0.68%	8.44%
Maldives	2.65%	0.87%	2.1%	0.5%	6.12%

Source: Author, Centennial (2008, 2009)

3.1. Investment Needs for High Priority Sustainable Projects

Based on the south Asian countries study, Bangladesh needs investment for high priority the field of including infrastructure, IT, energy and power, transportation, communication, chemical industry, textile and build 100 new economic zones by 2030. The government of Bangladesh promulgated the PPP law In August 2012, which provides a clear and transparent regulatory and procedural framework for the implementation of PPP projects and set up a special PPP Bureau under the office of the prime minister's office to be responsible for the selection and management of investors in national PPP projects. The Bangladesh government allows foreign investors to participate in infrastructure construction in Bangladesh through BOT, PPP, and other means which give national treatment to foreign investors. BOT and PPP projects can involve any social or economic infrastructure, such as ports, airports, roads, railways, bridges, power stations, and transmission lines in the field of energy. In GMS, there were some projects identified in South Asia, out of the projects in the transport sector, airport, and road infrastructure.

Payala 1320mw coal-fired power plant project in Bangladesh

The communication sector is a high priority for foreign investors in Bangladesh.

In August 2021, Bangladesh's first metro-rail in the capital of Dhaka made the trial run on a section of the 20.1-km project. Dhaka Mass Transit Company Limited (DMTCL), a Bangladeshi state-owned enterprise founded to implement the metro rail lines across Dhaka, is constructing the 20.1-km metro rail line, divided into eight packages, in collaboration with companies from China, Japan, and other countries. In February

2013, Bangladesh signed a loan deal with the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) to finance the metro rail project scheduled to be implemented in three phases.

Bangladesh's first Metro-rail Project, Dhaka, 2021

The construction of Bangladesh's largest Padma Bridge With the installation of the 150-meter-long span, 6.15 km of the bridge is now visible. Bangladesh's Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina inaugurated the main works of the Padma Bridge project, the biggest of its kind in the country, in December 2015.

Apart from connecting nearly 30 million people in Bangladesh's southwest region to the rest of the country, the 6.15-km Padma bridge will enhance regional trade and collaboration along with the Asian Highway No. 1 and the Trans-Asian railway network. It was the largest international bridge construction project that Chinese enterprises have ever undertaken, with a bid amount of 1.549 billion U.S. dollars.

Padma Bridge, one of the Bangladesh Dreams

3.2. Regional Cooperation in Trade-Related Infrastructure

The impacts of trade-related infrastructure can be leveraged by coordination across borders, taking advantage of economies of scope and scale to facilitate trade expansion. In the Greater Mekong Sub-region, special forums coordinate transport, telecommunications, and electric power infrastructure developments, particularly for cross-country economic corridors.

In the international context, harmonized and coordinated soft infrastructure will complement physical infrastructure connections. Supported by a conducive policy environment that capitalizes on regional externalities through cooperative arrangements, enhanced infrastructure services can reduce trade costs and facilitate trade expansion, regional integration, and economic development.

3.3. Efficiency, Comparative Advantage, and Production Fragmentation for infrastructure in South Asia

Sustainable infrastructure affects not only an absolute but also a comparative advantage for every country. Specialization and trade patterns depend in part on the quality of infrastructure services. Sustainable infrastructure services can alleviate the constraints of factor endowment and affect the dynamics of comparative advantage because services can supplement or replace physical inputs.

As sustainable infrastructure expanded in South Asia, trade costs fell and altered countries' comparative advantages, enabling greater fragmentation of production supply chains and inter-regional trade in parts and components. The subsequent economic integration is markedly higher than in other developing countries in South Asia (Table 8).

Table 8: Inter-regional Comparisons in South Asian Countries

Sector	Year	Africa	East Asia	South Asia	Latin America and the Caribbean
Merchandise trade (% of GDP)	2005	57.8	74.6	31.2	44.2
Intra-regional trade shares (%)	2003	12.2	55.0	6.0	15.0
Electricity consumption (kWh per capita)	2003	513.0	1,184	393.9	1,614.5
Electric power transmission and distribution losses (% of output)	2003	12.0	7.3	26.4	16.1
Paved roads (% of total)	1999–2003	12.5	32.3	53.9	26.8

Internet users (per 1,000)	2005	29.0	88.6	49.0	156.1
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Source: World Bank, World Development Indicators 2007.

As production processes become more decentralized, infrastructure services that ensure timely and reliable delivery become more critical. Similarly, South Asia performed better than other developing regions (Table 9).

Table 9: Border Trade Costs in South Asia

Sector	Sub-Saharan Africa	East Asia and Pacific	South Asia	Latin America and the Caribbean
Export documents (#)	8.2	6.9	8.1	7.3
Time to export (days)	40	23.9	34.4	22.2
Cost to export (US\$ per container)	1,561	885	1,236	1,068
Import documents (#)	12.2	9.3	12.5	9.5
Time to import (days)	51.5	25.9	41.5	27.9
Cost to import (US\$ per container)	1,947	1,037	1,495	1,226

3.4. Infrastructure for Supporting Inclusive Growth

The analytical framework in this section explores how infrastructure affects income equality, which is an important consideration of the impact of infrastructure on poverty. The analytical framework points out that sustainable infrastructure development promotes inclusive growth, thereby reducing poverty. Sustainable infrastructure development is achieved by (i) creating new job opportunities and economic activities, (ii) reducing production costs through improvements in transport and connectivity, (iii) expanding the overall production capacity, and (v) improving the use of key facilities. By increasing inclusiveness, infrastructure will reduce poverty directly or indirectly. The schematic representation of this framework is summarized in Figure 1.

Figure1: Average Productivity Growth and Infrastructure Availability

Notes: ARM=Armenia; BAN=Bangladesh; CAM=Cambodia; HKG=Hong Kong, China; IND=India; INO=Indonesia; KGZ=Kyrgyz Rep.; KOR=Rep. of Korea; MAL=Malaysia; MON=Mongolia; PAK=Pakistan; PHI=Philippines; PRC=People's Rep. of China; SIN=Singapore; SRI=Sri Lanka; TAP=Taipei,China; THA=Thailand; VIE=Viet Nam

Sources: S. Straub and A. Terada-Hagiwara. 2011. Infrastructure Growth in Developing Asia. Paper presented at the conference on Infrastructure for Inclusive Growth and Poverty Reduction at the Asian Development Bank. Manila.14-15 April. p. 2.

Table 10: Framework to Analyze Infrastructure for Inclusive Growth and Poverty Reduction

Note: PPP = public-private partnership. Source: Developed by the author.

3.5. Public-Private Partnerships in South Asia

PPP exists in a wide range of infrastructure development, including public utility services, transport, and the private sector, which can help provide citizens with better information and other services to improve governance. In some cases, the focus was on a strong public sector position, and the term "private sector

participation" was used. Sometimes, cooperation may focus on only one aspect, such as meeting financial requirements, construction, or service operation. Different forms of partnerships reflect the distinct distribution of responsibilities between the private and public sectors.

Table 11: Private Participation in Infrastructure, South Asia

Country	Total Investment, US\$ million	Number of Projects	Population, million	Income Category
Bangladesh	5,367	23.0	149.0	Lower M. Income
India	96,130	306.0	1,131.9	Low income
Nepal	404	8.0	27.8	Low income
Pakistan	21,715	47.0	169.3	Low income
Sri Lanka	2,640	22.0	20.1	Lower M. Income
Total	126,256	406	1498.1	

Source: World Bank. Private Participation in Infrastructure Database; and Population Reference Bureau. 2007. World Population Datasheet.

In South Asia, PPPs are important for telecommunications, energy, and transport.

Figure 2: Private Participation in Infrastructure situation in South Asia

Source: World Bank and PPIAF Project Database.

4. Challenges for Regional Infrastructure Financing

From 2010 to 2020, meeting the huge annual financing demand of US \$776 billion for national (US \$747 billion) and regional (US \$29 billion) infrastructure is one of the biggest challenges faced by many developing countries in South Asia. Continue to improve competitiveness and productivity by reducing trade

and logistics costs, forming specialized industrial clusters, and expanding and deepening production networks, all of which require high-quality national and regional infrastructure to succeed.

According to the most conservative estimates, the demand for infrastructure investment at the national level will reach a staggering \$2.37 trillion in the next decade for South Asia and \$8.3 trillion for the whole Asia. To attract investment, low-income countries may rely more on regional and international capital markets and donors (including bilateral and multilateral development banks) to provide additional financing, especially concessional financing.

The main challenge facing south Asia is to mobilize all available resources to finance "banking" infrastructure projects and to ensure strong coordination and cooperation among stakeholders at the national, regional, and sub-regional levels. It also needs to develop innovative financing mechanisms and modalities for participating countries, as well as policy, regulation, and capacity development (through human capital and institutional development).

The capacity building in less developed countries is important because regional infrastructure performs as well as its weakest links or participating countries. Another chapter of this book discusses the problems and challenges, and the role of south Asian financial market integration in infrastructure financing needs.

An interesting aspect of South Asia's economic diversity, as well as its special potential in regional energy and water infrastructure, it has both surplus and scarce resources. For example, Nepal and Bhutan represent energy surplus countries that could supply clean hydropower or natural gas to energy-deficient countries in the region, like Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan. In the face of the global financial crisis and resulting economic downturn, there is an increasing need for greater coordination of stimulus packages in sustainable infrastructure investment in transport, energy, water, and ITC to ensure cross-border projects are efficiently developed for enhancing regional connectivity. Regional infrastructure projects for building an integrated Asia are essential to harness shared resources and efficiency cost-effectively.

5. China's Investment Cooperation With South Asian Countries

5.1. Chinese economics current situation

China has changed from an international capital inflow into a powerful outflow country and already has become the second-largest foreign direct investment country in the world. China's economy will grow 6% in 2021, which is slower than 6.1% in 2019, according to estimates by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)¹.

That's consistent with the 'L-shaped recovery' and have been expecting for some time. That's because China's government has supported the economy with tax and interest rate cuts during the past year.

Figure 3: China: Real Economic Growth YoY (%), 2007-2024 (f)

Source: Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, November 2019

5.2. Chinese Investment Situation in South Asian Countries

From the perspective of China's investment in South Asian countries, China's investment in those countries is mainly realized through imperfect government-led investment, Multinational Enterprise FDI, and some bank loan channels. This kind of government-led investment and bank foreign lending investment is not open to China due to political concerns of some countries or pressure from third countries.

Release the investment authority of some industries, and even the invested projects may be terminated or delayed; South Asian countries' investment in China is a mainly direct investment and humanitarian assistance in times of disaster.

Table-12 China's Direct Investment in South Asian Countries—2007-2015

Source: world bank (<http : data.worldbank.org.cn />)

Country/ year	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
Bangladesh	364	450	1075	724	1032	3303	4137	2502	3119
Afghanistan	10	11391	1639	191	29554	1761	-122	2792	-326
India	2202	10188	- 2488	4761	18008	27681	14857	31718	70525
Pakistan	91063	26537	7675	33135	33328	8893	16357	101426	32074
Nepal	99	1	118	86	858	765	3697	4504	7888
Sri Lanka	-152	904	-140	2281	8123	1675	7177	8511	1747
Maldives	--	--	--	--	--	--	155	72	--

Although the international environmental situation in 2016 is not clear, the external environment of South Asia is still very strong in general. First, changes in international trade and capital flows have little impact on South Asian countries. Although the weakening of China's import demand has harmed the global market

and commodity prices, South Asia has only been slightly affected because they are not China's main importers.

Figure-3: International Economy and the Current Situation of the Internal and External Economic Environment in South Asia

Figure-4: China's Investments and Development in Clean Energy Generation Overseas

6. Bilateral Strategy for Connectivity

6.1. China–South Asian countries connectivity

The scope for strengthening connectivity between China and South Asia was established through “One Belt and One Road” by the respective government heads in 2013. China's economy is shifting its growth pattern from investment-led exports to consumer-led domestic demand growth. It is no longer merely a way of getting foreign cash and technology but a way for China to

strengthen its influence in global governance as an economic giant. This article seeks to analyze the possibilities of South Asian countries, especially Bangladesh's Belt and Road Initiative. The global BRI phenomenon is characterized in this perspective. This account of the activities of the ground describes what new BRI has brought to China's image.

6.2. China– Bangladesh Connectivity

Since 1975 the establishment of diplomatic relations between China and Bangladesh with bilateral relations maintained healthy development. One belt and One Road is the first one to be followed by one belt, one road south. One belt, one road south was signed by President Xi Jinping in October 2016. The two countries announced that the bilateral relations should be promoted as a strategic partnership and signed a “One Belt and One Road” cooperation Documents. Bangladesh is an important project contracting market for China; China has been the largest trading partner of Bangladesh for many years. In 2019, China ranked first in the increment of investment in Bangladesh and economic and trade cooperation promoted the healthy development of bilateral relations.

Creating a bright future together

LI JIMING

ON March 17, Bangladesh kicked off its 10-day series of celebrations of the birth centenary of the Father of the Nation Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman and

the golden jubilee of the country's independence. As a good friend of Bangladesh, China would definitely not be absent from such an event. Chinese President HE Xi Jinping sent a congratulatory video message, and extended, on behalf of the government and people of China, cordial greetings and best wishes to President Abdul Hamid, Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina, and the government and people of Bangladesh. This congratulatory video message bears special significance as it was the first time that President Xi ever recorded such a video for another country's domestic programme. It shows the great importance attached by President Xi himself to Bangladesh and China-Bangladesh relations.

As President Xi has pointed out, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman was an old and good friend of the Chinese people. He visited China twice in 1952 and 1957 and forged great friendships with Chairman Mao Zedong, Premier Zhou Enlai, and other Chinese leaders of the elder generation. The seed of China-Bangladesh friendship had been planted by the veteran leaders of the two countries long before diplomatic ties were established.

Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman is also no stranger to me. Since I assumed my duty as the Chinese Ambassador in Dhaka, I heard many touching stories about Bangabandhu, a great hero in Bangladeshi history and the founder and architect of Bangladesh. He dedicated his whole life to the welfare

of the Bangladeshi people even since his early childhood, and often gave away his personal effects to the people in need. He sacrificed his own life in the service of his beloved people and country. It is said that even after more than a half-century, a senior Bangladeshi lady can still remember every detail when she performed for Bangabandhu as a little girl. Indeed, Bangabandhu is fondly remembered by the people in Bangladesh to this day. The "Sonar

based on Bangabandhu's diary about his visit to China. After reading this book, I had a deep understanding of what the Honourable Prime Minister had mentioned to me several times on that day: Bangabandhu's many visions about China now have come true.

I was honoured to attend the grand event on March 17. President Xi said in his congratulatory video message that, "Do not forget who dug the well when drinking water from it." It described

Bangladesh. We firmly support each other on issues concerning our core interests. Recently, the two countries have been focusing on fighting against Covid-19, and China is ready to offer Bangladesh 500 thousand doses of Covid-19 vaccines as a gift, implementing the idea of building a community with a shared future for humanity.

As Prime Minister Hasina said at the event, Bangladesh should move forward further which is to make Bangladesh a developed and prosperous country by 2041. "Mujib Borsho" and the golden jubilee of the independence of Bangladesh is a new beginning of its "2041 Vision". 2021 is the 100th anniversary of the founding of the Communist Party of China and the first year of the "14th Five-Year Plan". Just a few days ago, the Fourth Session of the 13th National People's Congress of China had just voted through the 14th Five-Year Plan and the Outline of Long-term Goals for 2035. At present, both China and Bangladesh are standing at a new historical starting point, and we can go for a bright future together on the basis of traditional friendship.

China and Bangladesh are good partners in fighting the epidemic, in resuming work and production, and in national rejuvenation. China is willing to work with Bangladesh to implement the important consensus reached by the leaders of the two countries, promote the construction of a China-Bangladesh community of shared future and China-Bangladesh health community. China is also willing to work with Bangladesh to strengthen high-level exchanges and jointly build the "Belt and Road" cooperation, implement more projects that benefit people's livelihoods, and build the foundation of China-Bangladesh friendship. Let our two countries work hand in hand, based on the solid friendship built by our predecessors, to realise our goals.

HE Mr Li Jiming is Ambassador of China to Bangladesh.

PM Sheikh Hasina with Chinese President Xi Jinping.

PHOTO: STAR

Bangla" he envisioned is still galvanising the Bangladeshi people in their pursuit of national rejuvenation.

A few days ago, I handed over a bronze bust of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman to Her Excellency Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina, a special gift from the Chinese Embassy for the auspicious occasion of the celebration of his birth centenary. During the meeting, the Honourable Prime Minister gifted me a book written by Bangabandhu, "The new China I Saw". It is compiled

Bangabandhu's contributions to the China-Bangladesh friendship, and did impress me a lot. President Xi stressed, "now it is our sacred duty to pass on the baton to future generations." The Honourable Prime Minister also echoed positively to his speech.

Only friendships built on sincerity can last long. Since the establishment of diplomatic ties 46 years ago, China has always regarded Bangladesh as its true friend and partner for development. China highly values its relations with

The Daily Star News, On 17 March 2021.

6.3. Bangladesh Economic status

Bangladesh is one of the countries with the most dynamic economic development in South Asia and the world. Over the past decade, the average growth rate of GDP has remained above 6%, achieving economic growth of 8.15% in FY2019 and 5.24% in FY2020 under the influence of the epidemic.

Bangladesh is the second largest garment exporter in the world, and the garment processing industry is its pillar industry. At the end of 2019, Bangladesh's foreign exchange reserves reached US \$32.716 billion, second only to India among South Asian countries.

Bangladesh's economic development prospect is relatively bright, and the GDP growth rate of 6%-7% can be guaranteed. However, its economic development is still suffering from political conflict and uncertainty, imbalance in industry structure, as well as a poor recovery in terms of the global economy. All in all, within the next 10 years Bangladesh's economic development can be promising, and the annual GDP growth rate can be expected at 7%. Bangladesh just recently agreed to swap 200 million dollars worth of its currency with Sri Lanka for three months. China provided financial support to Sri Lanka in the form of a \$1 billion

loan and 1.5-billion-dollar currency exchange. The development of Bangladesh's economy is not the only reason for this desire to improve the country's image but also increase the economic situation day by day.

Figure-5,6: Yearly Growth Rate of GDP at Constant Price for FY2006 to FY2016

The proportion of Bangladesh's total investment in GDP is 30.47% in the fiscal year 2020 and 29.92% in 2021. The proportion of private investment in GDP is 22.06% in FY2020 and 21.25% in FY2021. The proportion of public investment in GDP is 8.41% in the fiscal year 2020 and 8.67% in 2021. Bangladesh's domestic savings accounted for 23.77% of GDP in fiscal 2020 and 24.17% in 2021.

According to the Bangladesh media report, Bangladesh's debt-GDP ratio was raised to 41% in 2020 which was 36% by the end of 2019. Bangladesh was borrowed from international financial institutions to fight the epidemic and protect people's livelihood, so that its debt- GDP ratio was raised to 41%, exceeding the safety threshold of the debt-GDP ratio of 40%.

Figure-7: Bangladesh's Debt-GDP ratio

6.4. Advantages of Attracting Foreign Investment in South Asia

Bangladesh is entering the ranks of developing countries. To consolidate its advantages in clothing, leather, medicine, and other industries, the government has continuously strengthened its investment in infrastructure and has potential market opportunities in the fields of electric power, light industry, textile, rail transit, automobile, communication, construction machinery, ship, and ocean engineering.

In terms of investment environment, to ensure sustainable economic development, Bangladesh attaches importance to attracting foreign investment and encourages private enterprises to participate more in economic construction. Bangladesh's advantages in attracting foreign investment are mainly reflected in the government's attention, preferential policies, rapid economic growth, large market potential, sufficient labor resources, and low price. According to the 2019 Global Competitiveness Report of the world economic forum, Bangladesh ranks 105th among the 141 most competitive countries in the world, and according to the 2020 business environment report of the world bank, Bangladesh ranks 168th among 190.

According to the data released by the government of Bangladesh, in the past 10 years, Bangladesh's economy continued to grow steadily, and the average annual growth rate of gross domestic product (GDP) remained above 6%. In the fiscal year 2018 / 19, Bangladesh's real GDP was 11.06 trillion Taka, its nominal GDP was 25.42 trillion Taka, its per capita GDP was about US \$1828, and its per capita income was about US \$1909 (calculated at the exchange rate of US \$1 to TK 84.03).

Table-13 : Macroeconomic Situation of Bangladesh in Recent Years

Fall year	Real GDP (TK trillion)	Economic growth Rate (%)	Nominal GDP (TK trillion)	Per capita GDP(Taka trillion)	per capita income(Taka trillion)
Fy14 / 15	8.25	6.55	15.16	9.60	10.22

Fy15/ 16	8.84	7.10	17.33	10.84	11.46
Fy16/ 17	9.48	7.28	19.76	12.22	12.74
Fy17 / 18	10.22	7.86	22.50	13.75	14.38
Fy18 / 19	11.06	8.15	25.42	15.36	16.04

Source: Bangladesh Bureau of statistics

Note: the above GDP growth rate is calculated according to the real GDP, and the per capita GDP and per capita income are calculated according to the nominal GDP and GNI.

6.5. China's Investment in Bangladesh for sustainable Infrastructure

The number of Chinese investments in Bangladesh is not especially significant before 2010, Bangladesh has received consideration since 2011. Between 1977 to 2010, China invested just 250 million dollars in Bangladesh and was around 200 million dollars in 2011. (Imam 2012). (The phrases "outward FDI" and "outward direct investment" are applied interchangeably in this article) After 2011, Chinese investment and trade are significantly increased in Bangladesh. Although it is still not a considerable number, it is nevertheless a significant statistic in Bangladesh.

In this case, there are several fascinating questions: **Does China regard Bangladesh as a significant investment place? How does Chinese investment review Bangladesh?**

Are Bangladesh-China good investment and international business partner?

Figure-8: Bangladesh –China Trade and Investment Figure

According to Bangladesh Economic Relations Bureau on October 26 in 2021, the Export-Import Bank of China and the Bangladesh government signed an export credit agreement worth US \$1.13 billion for Chinese preferential buyers on behalf of the Economic Relations Bureau for the construction of the long-awaited 24 miles four-lane elevated highway project from Dhaka Airport to Asulia. Shahazir, deputy secretary of Bangladesh Economic Relations Bureau, and Zhang Tianqin, deputy general manager of Export-Import Bank of China, signed the contract on behalf of both parties. According to the agreement, China provides Bangladesh with the loan for 25 years, including a 5-year grace period, a 20-year repayment period, and the loan interest of 2%.

Dhaka– Ashulia elevated expressway, Chinese investment project in BD

6.6. Trade Analysis Between China and Bangladesh

From January to August 2021, the bilateral import and export volume of goods between them was US \$1520.03 million, an increase of US \$5739.3363 million compared with the same period in 2020, a year-on-year increase of 60.4%.

Figure-9: Import and Export Volume Analysis Between China and Bangladesh 2015 -2021

Data source: China Customs

6.6.1. Trade Balance Statistics Between China and Bangladesh

From January to August in 2021, the trade balance between China and Bangladesh was 13,812,984,900 US dollars, and that same period in 2020 was 14,260,464,000 US dollars.

Figure-10: Balance Between China and Bangladesh in August 2015-2021

Data source: China Customs

6.6.2. Monthly Statistics of Imports and Exports Between China and Bangladesh

In August 2021, the import and export volume of goods between China and Bangladesh was US \$220.23852 million, an increase of US \$91.40872 million compared with the same period in 2020, in which the total value of China's exports to Bangladesh was US \$210.59433 million, the total value of China's imports from Bangladesh was US \$96.442 million, and the trade balance between China and Bangladesh was US \$200.95013 million.

Table-14 Statistics of Import and Export Between China and Bangladesh

Month	Total import and export (USD)	Total export China to Bangladesh (USD)	Total import China to Bangladesh(USD)	Trade difference (USD)
Sep. 2020	143214.1	136056.2	7157.9	128898.3
Oct.	138970.6	133217.7	5752.9	127464.8
Nov.	169195.8	161866.8	7329.0	154537.8
Dec.	189133.3	180909.2	8224.2	172685.0
Jan. 2021	184980.3	175915.6	9064.6	166851.0
Feb.	154943.0	148083.1	6859.8	141223.3
March	162185.4	150989.4	11196.0	139793.3
April	215596.5	208015.4	7581.1	200434.4
May	198506.0	189424.0	9082.0	180342.0
June	200958.4	192727.8	8230.6	184497.2
July	182144.0	174439.9	7704.0	166735.9
August	220238.5	210594.3	9644.2	200950.1

6.7. Difficulties and Challenges Faced by the Foreign Investor in Bangladesh

Opportunities and challenges coexist for Chinese enterprises to carry out economic and trade cooperation in Bangladesh. Bangladesh's backward infrastructure, insufficient energy resources, low labor quality, low degree of industrialization, business environment to be improved and fragile ecological environment are unfavorable factors for Chinese enterprises to invest and cooperate in Bangladesh.

6.7.1. Brief Introduction of Investment and Contracting Projects of Chinese Enterprises in Bangladesh

According to the statistics of China's Ministry of Commerce, in 2019, China's direct investment in Bangladesh was US \$375 million. By the end of 2019, the stock of China's direct investment in Bangladesh

was US \$1.248 billion. The investment fields involve power, highway, clothing, textile, ceramics, etc., but mainly focus on infrastructure, textile and clothing, and related mechanical equipment. The main investment enterprises include China Machinery Import and Export Corporation, North International Cooperation Co., Ltd., Lidecheng Garment Company, New Hope Bangladesh Co., Ltd.

Contracting project, according to the statistics of China's Ministry of Commerce in 2019, Chinese enterprises signed 284 new contracts in Bangladesh with an amount of USD 13.484 billion and a turnover of USD 5.303 billion. The newly signed large-scale engineering contracting projects include the phase II project of a 2X1000MW ultra-supercritical coal-fired power station in Purbari, Bangladesh. It was undertaken by Sinohydro International Engineering Co., Ltd and Northern International Cooperation Co., Ltd. It was also undertaken 1320 (2 * 660MW) coal-fired power plant project in Boduakali, Bangladesh.

6.7.2. Difficulties and Challenges for Foreign Enterprises

Bangladesh has sufficient cheap local labor supply, but its overall quality is not high, operation ability and skill level is low, which can't meet the high-level work requirements. Its competitiveness is mainly in the low-end manufacturing industry. According to statistics, 40% to 50% of Bangladesh's labor force is distributed in the field of agriculture. In recent years, the minimum wage and labor cost has increased. Bangladesh also hasn't enough electricity, natural gas, and other energy supplies and it is difficult to ensure the access and capacity expansion of new enterprises, in this cause affecting industrial production.

In addition, Bangladesh needs to maintain an easy tax system and work visa processing for foreigners, the visa processing and approval time is long now. So, the requirement to make an easier tax system for the foreign investor should be considered in the current period.

7. Role of Multilateral Institutions in Supporting Infrastructure Development in South Asia

The role of multilateral institutions in financing and supporting infrastructure activities in the developing world is extremely important. The contribution of multilateral institutions like World Bank, ADB, AIIB, NDB, African Development Bank, Inter-American Development Bank, and the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development in infrastructure development.

7.1. World Bank's Role in Infrastructure Development in South Asia

The World Bank has funded many projects to develop infrastructure in the whole world. Being cognizant of it must play a key role in meeting the global demand for infrastructure financing and policy advice, the World Bank has placed infrastructure at the forefront and center of its development agenda to reduce poverty and stimulate economic growth. The World Bank has developed an infrastructure action plan that includes innovative ways to finance infrastructure projects.

In the global value chain, the international trading system is particularly important in the world. Global value chains cross national boundaries, and the policy actions or omissions of one country may affect producers and consumers in other countries. The World Bank helps to deal with the spillover effects of national policies and achieve better development. When goods and services are transferred across national borders, the costs caused by trade protection will be amplified. Therefore, the benefits of coordinated

reduction of trade barriers to global value chains are even greater than those of standard trade. Given the inseparable link between foreign investment and global value chains, the creation of an open and secure investment environment is essential for participation in global value chains, especially for capital in poor countries.

In the fiscal year 2021, the World Bank approved \$5.9 billion in lending to the region for 51 operations, including \$4.6 billion in International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (IBRD) commitments and \$1.3 billion in International Development Agency (IDA) commitments. The World Bank also approved IBRD's new lending commitments amounted to \$30.5 billion for 125 operations, of which seven were IBRD and IDA blended operations.

In South Asian countries, the World Bank has played an important role in funding infrastructure in the region. The World Bank approved nearly US\$9.409 billion for South Asian countries in 2021. Out of this, US\$3.665 billion from IBRD and US\$5.744 billion in IDA which was commitments US\$10.873 billion.

Message from the WB's Executive Directors

The past year has been immensely challenging around the world—especially for developing countries—as the COVID-19 pandemic reversed decades of progress in ending extreme poverty, achieving shared prosperity, and reducing inequality. The World Bank Group responded swiftly and extensively to the health, economic, and social impacts of the crisis to help spur recovery. But more needs to be done to address the needs of the marginalized and those who live in the poorest areas. The Board discussed and approved

several important initiatives and programs in support of both countries' immediate needs and their long-term development goals.

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Vaccines. We have made key and timely decisions on proposals by Bank Group management to respond to the pandemic and finance vaccination efforts, including mechanisms for prompt delivery. The Bank Group is partnering with WHO, COVAX, UNICEF, and others, including private manufacturers, to help facilitate transparent, affordable, and fair access to vaccines for developing countries and to continue strengthening global preparedness for future pandemics.

Assisting the poor. To help start the process of recovery, the Bank Group registered a historic increase in the delivery of lending for projects and initiatives to assist low- and middle-income countries, including small states, in tackling multifaceted challenges, safeguarding human capital, and providing social safety nets to target their most vulnerable people.

Given the immense financing needs, we agreed to bring forward the IDA20 replenishment process, which we expect will be completed by December 2021. In addition, we approved an update to the World Bank's Operational Policy 2.30 (Development Cooperation and Fragility, Conflict, and Violence) to help implement the Bank Group's Strategy for Fragility, Conflict, and Violence. At the 2021 Spring Meetings, the Development Committee also asked the Bank to scale up its work to address rising levels of food insecurity and to support countries in achieving Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 2, and nutrition for all, along with other partners.

Green, resilient, and inclusive development. The Bank Group continues to support countries in achieving the twin goals of ending extreme poverty and boosting shared prosperity. In responding to the COVID-19 crisis, the Bank Group has an opportunity to help low- and middle-income countries build the foundations for a strong and durable recovery based on a framework that we discussed, which supports green, resilient, and inclusive development. We believe that this, in turn, can help address the longer-term challenge of climate change.

Climate. We hope that the ambitious new targets for climate financing outlined in the Climate Change Action Plan 2021–25 and the alignment of the Bank Group's financing with the Paris agreement—complemented by the approach to green, resilient, and inclusive development and efforts to build long-term resilience for food security—will help deliver on the twin goals and the SDGs.

Knowledge framework. We welcomed the discussion of the new Strategic Framework for Knowledge, which strives to better integrate knowledge into solutions for clients and the global community. We look forward to implementation of this framework, which will strengthen the Bank Group's role as a source of solutions.

Debt. As countries face increasing debt burdens, our Governors, together with the IMF, have given the Bank Group a mandate to address fiscal and debt distress in IDA countries in a way that supports green, resilient, and inclusive development and poverty reduction. We are hopeful that the G20 Common Framework, along with extension of the Debt Service Suspension Initiative to the end of 2021, will allow beneficiary countries to dedicate more resources to tackling the crisis, investing in health care and education, promoting growth, and improving their long-term approaches on debt.

Private sector. Recognizing growing credit constraints, the private sector is a critical player in helping client countries attain their development goals, create and develop markets, mobilize resources, and respond to COVID-19, including through IFC's Global Health Platform and MIGA's response programs. We expect the Bank Group to keep building partnerships across a common strategic framework to help generate private sector solutions that address development challenges.

Racial justice. There were important efforts this year to address racial injustice within the Bank Group and with our clients, including a set of recommendations put forth by the End Racism Task Force to fight racism and racial discrimination. We look forward to implementation of these recommendations through an action plan that will reaffirm this institutional value, which is embedded in the Bank Group's Code of Ethics.

Accountability mechanisms. We also reaffirmed the importance of accountability mechanisms for people and communities who believe that they have been, or are likely to be, adversely affected by Bank Group projects and investments. We have approved enhancements to the Bank Group's social and environmental accountability framework, including changes to the World Bank Inspection Panel's toolkit and to the reporting line of the Compliance Advisor Ombudsman for IFC and MIGA.

Leadership, staff, and return to office. November 2020 marked the transition to a new term for the Board of Executive Directors, and in February we welcomed Makhtar Diop as IFC Managing Director and Executive Vice President.

We look forward to the widespread availability of COVID-19 vaccines across the globe, the safe return of the Bank Group's staff to the office, and the overall return to a new normal. Our utmost appreciation goes to the staff for their ongoing dedication to the Bank Group's mission and their perseverance and hard work over the past year, despite the immense and sudden change in their working environments and their lives.

The World Bank Group remains ready to help our clients on the path to recovery. We hope that the new fiscal year brings good health and strong development outcomes for all.

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From the world Bank Annual Report 2021.

7.2. AIIB's Role in Sustainable Infrastructure Development in South Asia

The Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB) is a multilateral development bank whose mission is financing the Infrastructure for Tomorrow—infrastructure with sustainability at its core and AIIB began operations in Beijing in January 2016.

In 2020, AIIB total approved 45 projects to US\$10 billion financings, of which US\$2.9 billion was for infrastructure projects excluding COVID-19 Crisis Recovery Facility. In 2020, AIIB's climate finance totaled US\$1.2 billion or 41 percent of total infrastructure financing approved, excluding projects financed through the Facility.

The Bank aims to achieve its 2025 climate finance target by scaling up efforts to develop and finance low-carbon, climate-resilient projects, in partnership with clients and co-financiers from the public and private

sector. AIIB will continue to be active in joint MDB working groups and in international fora on combatting climate change.

PPSF has provided project preparation support to a total of US\$1.20 billion for seven member countries—Bangladesh, Lao People’s Democratic Republic, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan—Out of the around US\$390.711 in south Asia.

8. Conclusions

The importance of sustainable world economic interactions in today’s overseas economy cannot be overemphasized. The impact of COVID-19 for sustainable infrastructure, FDI, debt, trade, and exchange rates have a significant influence on economic activities in almost all countries in the world. However, the effect of sustainable infrastructure, FDI, and international trade are more noticeable across emerging economies compared to developed economies. In the same way, governments, especially from low-income and low-middle-income countries in South Asia, seek debt and development assistance from foreign countries and multilateral agencies to boost domestic resources to match the investment and international trade demand. This study suggests that to sustain economic growth through FDI, countries could adopt policies that will create an enabling political and economic environment suitable for international trade and economic activities to flourish and grow. Such policy includes maintaining a stable environment for investment, exchange rates, and major sustainable infrastructural development. Strong financial and legal institutions are attractive scenes for foreign investors. Furthermore, effort should be made towards mobilizing domestic resources to resolve economic challenges. This will build economies to a self-sustainable level of development, which is a major target of most global governmental authorities.

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Appendix A

Table A 1. List of countries in the sample

Low–Income	Lower–Middle–Income	Upper–Middle–Income	High–Income
Afghanistan	Angola	Albania	Antigua and Barbuda
Benin	Bangladesh	Algeria	Aruba
Burkina Faso	Bhutan	Argentina	Australia
Burundi	Bolivia	Armenia	Austria
African Republic	Cabo Verde	Azerbaijan	Bahamas
Chad	Cambodia	Belarus	Bahrain
Congo	Cameroon	Belize	Barbados
Eritrea	Comoros	Bosnia	Belgium
Ethiopia	Djibouti	Bulgaria	Bermuda
Guinea–Bissau	Egypt	China	Cayman Islands
Haiti	El Salvador	Colombia	Chile
Korea	Eswatini	Costa Rica	Croatia
Liberia	Ghana	Cuba	Cyprus
Madagascar	Honduras	Dominica	Czech Republic
Malawi	India	Dominican Rep	Denmark
Mali	Indonesia	Ecuador	Estonia
Mozambique	Kenya	Guinea	Finland
Nepal	Kiribati	Fiji	France
Niger	Kyrgyz Republic	Gabon	French Polynesia

Rwanda	Lao PDR	Georgia	Germany
Sierra Leone	Lesotho	Grenada	Greece
Somalia	Mauritania	Guatemala	HK SAR, China
South Sudan	Micronesia	Guyana	Hungary
Syrian	Moldova	Iran Islamic Rep	Iceland
Tajikistan	Mongolia	Iraq	Ireland
Tanzania	Morocco	Jamaica	Israel
Togo	Myanmar	Jordan	Italy
Uganda	Nicaragua	Kazakhstan	Japan
Yemen	Nigeria	Kosovo	Korea, Rep.
	Pakistan	Lebanon	Kuwait
	Papua New Guinea	Libya	Latvia
	Philippines	Malaysia	Lithuania
	Sao Tome and Principe	Maldives	Luxembourg
	Senegal	Marshall	Macao SAR, China
	Solomon Islands	Mauritius	Malta
	Sudan	Mexico	Netherlands
	Timor–Leste	Montenegro	New Caledonia
	Tunisia	Namibia	New Zealand
	Ukraine	Nauru	Mariana Islands
	Uzbekistan	North Macedonia	Norway
	Vanuatu	Paraguay	Oman
	Vietnam	Peru	Palau
	Gaza	Romania	Panama
	Zambia	Russian	Poland
	Zimbabwe	Samoa	Portugal
		Serbia	Puerto Rico
		South Africa	Qatar
		Sri Lanka	San Marino
		St. Lucia	Saudi Arabia
		Suriname	Singapore

Thailand
Tonga
Turkey
Venezuela, RB
Slovak Rep.
Slovenia
Spain
Sweden
Switzerland
Trinidad and Tobago
United Arab
Emirates
United Kingdom
United States
Uruguay

Appendix B: Compendium of Investment Needs of Regional Infrastructure Projects by Sub-region and by Program

Table B1. List of Investment Needs of Regional Infrastructure Projects

Region(s) Connected	Reg. program	Primary Country	Sector	Project	Invest ment Need (US\$ Million)
South Asia	TAR	Bangladesh	Rail	Dohazari–Gundum	N/A
South Asia	TAR	Bangladesh	Rail	Dhaka–Laksham chord line	200.0
South Asia	TAR	Bangladesh	Rail	Chinkiaastana–Laksham section	70.0
South Asia	TAR	Bangladesh	Rail	Linecapacity improvement Dhaka–Tongi	5.0
South Asia	TAR	Bangladesh	Rail	Strengthening of Jamuna Bridge	25.0
South Asia	TAR	Bangladesh	Rail	18 stations along Abdulpur– Parbatipur	22.0

South Asia	TAR	Bangladesh	Rail	19 stations along Chittangong–Akhaura	25.0
South Asia	AH	Bangladesh	Road	Beldanga–Panchagarh	9.0
South Asia	AH	Bangladesh	Road	Chittagong–Cox’s Bazar–Ramu–Gundam	144.0
South Asia	AH	Bangladesh	Road	Dasuria–Paksey–Kushtia	4.0
South Asia	AH	Bangladesh	Road	Daukandi–Chittagong	191.0
South Asia	AH	Bangladesh	Road	Jhenaidah–Jessore	5.0
South Asia	AH	Bhutan	Road	Phuentsholing–Thimphu double laning	60.0
South Asia	AH	India	Rail	Dedicated Freight Corridors	7,800.0
South Asia	AH	India	Rail	Jiribam–Kalay	649.0
South Asia	AH	India	Rail	Moreh (India)/Tamu (Myanmar)	1.0
South Asia	AH	India	Road	India–Nepal border	2.0
South Asia	AH	India	Road	Madurai–Dhanushkodi	6.0
South Asia	AH	India	Road	Shillong–Dwaki	2.0
South Asia	AH	India	Road	Siliguri–Fulbari Mod–Border of BD	80.0
South Asia	AH	Nepal	Road	Naubise–Thanko	24.0
South Asia	AH	Nepal	Road	Pathalaiya–Dhalkebar	
South Asia	AH	Nepal	Road	Kathmandu–Birgunj ICD link road	31.0
South Asia	Other	Regional	Energy	BD–Bhutan–Nepal–India Multilateral Power Line	9.0
South Asia	Other	Regional	Energy	Bangladesh–India Power Project	1,025.0

South Asia	Other	Regional	Energy	Bhutan–India HPP Projects	3,744.1
South Asia	Other	Regional	Energy	Green Power Development, Bhutan	334.5
South Asia	SASAC	Regional	Logistic	SASEC Information Highway Project	24.0
South Asia	SASAC	Regional– Bangladesh	Logistic	Transport Logistics & Trade Facilitation project	23.0
South Asia	SASAC	Regional– Bhutan		Transport Logistics & Trade Facilitation Project	48.0
South Asia	TAR	Sri–Lanka	Rail	Coast Line	N/A
South Asia	TAR	Sri–Lanka	Rail	Connecting Line	N/A
South Asia	TAR	Sri–Lanka	Rail	Northern Line	N/A
South Asia	AH	Sri–Lanka	Road	Land bridge connecting Sri Lanka and India	880.0
South Asia	AH	Sri–Lanka	Road	Talaimannar– Medawachchiya	36.0
South Asia	SASAC	Regional	TF / Logistics	Sub–regional Transport Logistics & Trade Facilitation Project (India)	50.0
South Asia	SASAC	Regional	TF / Logistics	SASEC Information Highway Project	24.0

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